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Method for quantification of microplastic release from plastic-based materials during weathering

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Abstract

Most microplastics (MPs) are generated as a result of photodegradation during the life of plastic products and after the end-of-life as mismanaged waste. At present, it is impossible to avoid plastic-based materials altogether because of their unique properties, versatility, and price. An option is to set limits on how much MPs these materials can release over their lifetime, which would not only reduce MPs pollution, but also improve product quality. However, there is a lack of reliable methodologies for assessing the generation of MPs from these products during use or when they are left as unmanaged waste. The objective of this study was to develop a novel method to assess (collect and quantify) MPs formation from plastic-based materials during weathering. The developed process design is based on a well-established accelerated weathering tester that has been modified by incorporation of a sieve system and water recirculation. The case study is carried out on a recycled polypropylene (rPP) and wood plastic composite (WPC) made from wood particles and the same rPP. Despite the lower plastic content, WPC released significantly more MPs (up to 9.4 g/m²) than the rPP (up to 0.3 g/m²) in the same weathering conditions and duration. Examination of the degraded surfaces revealed that the wood particles facilitated the release of MPs most likely due to moisture fluctuations causing wood swelling induced internal stresses. The collected MPs were mainly below 500 µm and their properties were different comparing to MPs made by cryogenic milling. PY-GC-MS did not detect MPs smaller than 20 µm that could pass through the smallest sieve and end up in the effluent. The reproducibility of the measured MPs release using the process design was very good during the tested weathering period, with variations of less than 7%.

Keywords Microplastics, Plastic, Wood plastic composites, Weathering, Quantification

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Introduction

The widespread presence of microplastics (MPs) across various ecosystems, along with growing evidence of their adverse impacts on the environment and human health, highlights the need for comprehensive mitigation strategies. These should include restrictions on specific sources, as well as limitations on activities or conditions that pose a high risk of MPs formation. The tiny solid plastic particles are classified in three groups by size: large MPs (5 mm–1 mm), MPs (1 mm–1 μ m), and nanoplastics (< 1 μ m) [1]. Emerging evidence suggests that MPs contribute to or exacerbate a range of health conditions, including cardiovascular, intestinal, pulmonary, oncological, infectious, and inflammatory diseases [2]. By entering the human body via ingestion, inhalation, or dermal contact, these plastic particles subsequently can accumulate in various tissues and organs [3]. Depending on their size the effects on living organisms can differ, generally, with more negative impact for the smaller particles [4]. Not only the size of MPs is a concern, but even more alarming is their chemical composition. MPs may contain harmful substances introduced through additives, residual monomers, and catalysts [5]. Furthermore, due to high surface area, MPs have strong adsorption capacity binding and transporting various hazardous compounds such as persistent organic pollutants (POPs), heavy metals, and antibiotics [6–8]. The co-occurrence of MPs and such contaminants increase toxicity and bioaccumulation potential, alters microbial communities, and adversely affects ecosystems [9].

Building materials have received relatively little attention on their potential MPs emissions, and therefore, also reduction and limitation measures are not introduced at legislative level. It has been reported that a significant number of MPs can be emitted from products such as plastic sheets, paints, plastic fibre-reinforced materials, composites, insulation etc [10]. Paints have been suggested to contribute to MPs pollution more than textile [11]. Recently wood plastic composites (WPCs), which are experiencing rapid market growth, have also shown indications of potential MPs release, at least for unprotected compositions [12]. However, the exact amount of MPs has not been quantified, which can differ depending on the material and its composition. Similarly, other plastic-based products (reusable cutlery, toys, furniture etc.) can degrade during weathering and release MPs, but these aspects have had little attention so far. Methods have been developed for fabrics that allows capturing, quantifying, and analysing released MPs during washing [13–16]. Methods for capturing airborne MPs from municipal solid waste transfer stations have been developed [17]. There are gravimetric approaches for tyres quantifying MPs release based on mass losses [18]. However, still a lot of materials that can potentially release

MPs have not been even considered as a source, potentially due to lack of methods and technology available to analyse these emissions. MPs release during weathering is one of the pathways that can potentially cause significant MPs emissions. However small attention has been attributed in this direction without established techniques for MPs quantification. Therefore, it is difficult to find information on how much MPs are released from different types of materials due to weathering and how the release changes during long-term use of corresponding products. Development of a reliable method could provide the opportunity to compare the release under the same testing conditions. This would make a significant contribution for optimizing compositions aimed at reducing MPs pollution.

One of the ways to develop a suitable method for MPs quantification efficiently is to somehow base the process on existing standardized tests. There are well established standard testing methods (e.g. ISO, ASTM) and devices (e.g. Q-Lab, Atlas) for material weathering, but these methods only cover the changes in material properties, but not the release of chemicals or small particles such as MPs. However, research is ongoing in this direction, and some results are available. Leaching of preservatives from treated wood has been studied by collecting the run-off water during simulated weathering tests [19]. Micropollutant release from building materials (metal sheets of stainless steel, copper, zinc, galvanised steel, corten steel, corrugated and coated steel, coated zinc; bitumen-based roofing felt and shingles; polyvinyl chloride sheets) have been studied by collecting rainwater and snowmelts [20]. Photodegradation products have been studied in leachates formed during weathering of plastics [21, 22]. Loss of additives from paints and weathered MPs have been evaluated [23, 24]. Menger et al. analysed the release of chemicals, heavy metals, and MPs from various plastic products cut to the size below 5 mm during artificial weathering in water medium [25]. They found that most of the products released chemicals and heavy metals as well as observed that the plastic pieces fragmented to even smaller MPs. However, MPs release was not quantified. Kang et al. has tried to estimate the MPs release indirectly through surface roughness measurements from various interior finishing materials exposed to UV radiation [26]. They observed that the potential release differed between these materials with the highest release for decorative tiles of almost 16 μ m/m². However, indirect approaches cannot disregard the influence of volatile product formation, chemocrystallisation or other processes that may cause surface embrittlement [27, 28]. Theoretically, all plastic-based materials can produce MPs. However, depending on the type of material, composition, and conditions, the release of MPs can start sooner or later and the extent can differ as well. It has

been suggested that the lack of scientific consensus on quantitative reporting approaches increases the difficulty of regulating MPs exposure in the environment [10]. This information is particularly important when different materials need to be compared in terms of their MPs pollution potential. It can also serve as a tool for reducing unintentional MPs emissions by restricting the use of high-contributing materials, or for demonstrating applicability when legislative limits are introduced.

The main objective of this study is to develop a method to assess MPs formation from plastic-based materials during weathering with the ability to collect and quantify MPs. Current weathering standards (ISO 4892, ASTM G154, EN 927, etc.) focus on assessing surface changes of materials rather than potential emissions, including MPs release. Plastic and WPCs, which have previously been shown to release MPs, are used as model materials for reaching the objective. Based on standard devices (weathering chambers) used to evaluate the weathering characteristics of materials in combination with MPs accumulation techniques, potentially a reliable method can be developed to compare and rank different materials in terms of their MPs formation potential under the same reproducible conditions. Additionally, the process design can provide real MPs for other studies as their formation occurs in conditions that are close to realistic including only the main natural stressors and avoiding unnatural manipulations (milling, grinding, synthesis, precipitation from solutions). In order to understand how the collected MPs differ from the MPs obtained by cryogenic milling, which are commonly used for risk assessment studies, the latter were also prepared and analysed. By cryogenic milling obtained MPs will be referred to as “artificial MPs” in this publication.

Materials and methods

Plastic-based material

Two types of plastic-based materials were chosen for this study: recycled polypropylene (rPP) and WPCs made of 60 wt% rPP and 40 wt% pine wood particles. rPP was kindly provided by a local recycled plastic manufacturer “Nordic Plast”. The specific plastic was chosen as it showed the highest degradation potential in our previous study [27]. To prepare WPC samples, pine wood (*Pinus sylvestris* L.) was milled in a Heavy-Duty Mill (Retsch, Germany) to reach a particle size that passes through a 1 mm sieve. The milled wood particles were then fractionated to obtain wood particles with the size 400–1000 μm by using a AS 200 vibratory sieve shaker (Retsch, Germany). Before compounding, the wood particles were dried in an oven at 103 ± 2 °C for 24 h. The dried wood particles were added to the rPP melt in a LRM-S-110/3E two-roll mill (LabTech, Thailand). During compounding, no additives were added. The roll temperatures were 180 °C and 185 °C, with rotational speeds of 10 rpm and 20 rpm, respectively. The produced WPC material after two-roll mill was pelletized for further processing. Compression moulding (180 °C, 2.0 MPa) in a LAP 450 hydraulic press (Joos, Germany) was used to prepare 1 mm thick WPC and rPP samples measuring 80 mm \times 75 mm. For each weathering experiment, 48 samples were prepared. For WPCs, two batches with identical composition were analysed (WPC1 and WPC2) to evaluate the reproducibility of the developed testing method. The obtained samples are presented in Fig. 1.

The absolutely dry mass of the samples for mass loss determination was obtained by drying the samples before the test and periodically after the first, second, fourth, and eight AW cycle by placing the samples in an oven at 60 °C for 12 h and then cooling the samples to room temperature in a desiccator above P_2O_5 powder. The residual moisture content in the samples was determined

Fig. 1 The prepared samples of wood plastic composite (WPC1 and WPC2) and recycled polypropylene (rPP) for accelerated weathering tests

indirectly by using additional samples specifically designed for this purpose, which also were dried together with other samples at 60 °C for 12 h, then weighed, and finally dried at 103 °C for 24 h to obtain the absolute dry mass. These samples were excluded from further testing. The residual moisture content was always considered when the samples were characterised during the weathering tests, therefore the calculated mass loss was based on the absolute dry mass.

It should be noted that WPCs without any functional additives were used in the study, except for those contained in the polymer matrix of the used rPP. Therefore, the weathering behaviour including MPs formation rates and amounts from real WPC products, depending on their composition, can substantially differ from the results presented in this paper. The study only evaluates the reliability of a proposed method that could be used for assessment and comparison of potential MPs release risk from plastic-based materials due to weathering.

Process design for assessment of MPs release during weathering

The weathering process is based on the well-established weathering device QUV Accelerated Weathering Tester (Q-Lab, USA), which is widely used for standard weathering tests (ISO, ASTM etc.). The process design extends the use of the device to evaluate and quantify MPs release (size 4000 μm –20 μm) by integrating a sieve and water

recirculation systems. Schematic representation of the novel process design is presented in Fig. 2a and the main steps are as follows:

1. Specimen preparation with appropriate size;
2. Rinsing the system with deionised water and changing the water filters;
3. Filling the system with deionised water, assembling the sieve system, and inserting the specimens;
4. Performing the test by exposing the samples to artificial weathering (AW) cycles (detailed flowchart about the steps is presented in Fig. 2b);
5. Removal of specimens, sieves and run-off water for further analysis.

Samples with the total exposed surface area of 0.23 m² were subjected to eight AW cycles (2 months) during which periodically MPs were collected and the samples characterised. The duration of one AW cycle is one week, which involves several steps of UV irradiation and water spray (Fig. 2b). During one AW cycle, the samples are exposed to 140 h of UV irradiation 4 h of water spray. The UV irradiation during the test is ensured by the UVA-340 type fluorescent lamps. The lamps provided a good simulation of sunlight in the short wavelength region from 295 nm to 365 nm with a peak emission at 340 nm. The UV radiation flux density at 340 nm was set to 1.30 W/m². The chamber temperature was 60 °C throughout the

Fig. 2 The developed process design for evaluating microplastic release during weathering; **(a)** schematic illustration of the developed process design; **(b)** flowchart of the artificial weathering (AW) cycle; i = sub-cycle index

test. The water flow rate during the spraying was 6–7 L/min. Around 25 L of distilled water was circulating the system and the amount was kept constant throughout the test by adding additional distilled water during the test.

Collection and quantification of the eroded material

The eroded material was collected in the integrated sieve system during the spray cycle of the weathering test when all of the run-off water was directed through the system. In the process, the eroded particles ($>20\ \mu\text{m}$) were separated and fractionated depending on their size, which corresponds to the mesh size of the sieves (4000 μm , 500 μm , 150 μm , 75 μm , 20 μm). The mass of the collected particles was determined as a difference between the dry mass of clean sieves and the dry mass of sieves with the collected particles. The drying was performed in an oven at $60 \pm 1\ ^\circ\text{C}$ for 24 h and the mass was determined on an analytic balance with the precision 0.0001 g. The results were expressed as the mass of the collected MPs (size $>20\ \mu\text{m}$) per square meter of the exposed surface (g/m^2), hereinafter referred as MPs release. This was the main indicator characterising MPs formation in this study. Finally, the collected particles were accurately transferred from the sieves to vials for further analysis. The contamination in the sieves from the surrounding environment was reduced to minimum by deep cleaning of the device before each test. Slight error was observed due to the weighing procedure of the sieves, which caused fluctuations of around $\pm 0.05\ \text{g}/\text{m}^2$ detected in the blank run experiments. This means that the setup at the current design has limitations on detecting relatively small amounts of MPs without incorporation of additional measures.

To detect MPs smaller than $20\ \mu\text{m}$, 20% (5 L) of the circulating run-off water was used. From this volume, most of the water was removed by evaporation under reduced pressure to obtain a concentrated water sample of around 100 ml. The samples were dried at $60 \pm 1\ ^\circ\text{C}$ to obtain the solids. These solids then were used for analysis by Py-GC-MS. More details about the methods are provided in Supplementary material S1. As in the weathering system a 5 micro filter was used for the protection of the spray nozzles from clogging, this fraction from 5 to $20\ \mu\text{m}$ partly may be removed from the run-off water [29].

Preparation of artificial MPs

Prior to cryogenic milling, the rPP pellets were grounded in a Heavy-Duty Knife Mill (Retsch, Germany) to obtain particles that pass through a 1 mm sieve. The coarse powder was then milled using a Cryogenic Mixer Mill (Retsch, Germany) in a stainless-steel grinding jar equipped with 6 stainless-steel balls. One cryogenic milling cycle consisted of 15 min milling at 5 Hz, 10 min milling at 25 Hz, and 2 min milling at 5 Hz. In total, 6

consecutive cycles were performed. Afterwards, the fine plastic powder was sieved to obtain the same five fractions (20 μm , 75 μm , 150 μm , 500 μm , and 4000 μm) as for the collected MPs. Part of the artificial MPs were transferred to a Petri dish, uniformly distributed, and exposed to UV irradiation in a QUV accelerated weathering tester (Q-Lab, USA) equipped with UVA-340 type fluorescent lamps with an irradiation intensity of $1.30\ \text{W}/\text{m}^2$ at 340 nm, to understand if with such an approach it is possible to obtain MPs with characteristics similar to those formed due to weathering and collected on sieves.

Characterisation of the plastic-based material sheet samples

The mass loss of the samples was determined after the 1st, 2nd, 4th, and 8th AW cycles. This was done according to the procedure described in the Sect. "2.1". Since the degradation occurs only on the exposed surface and this is the only area responsible for the mass loss, the cumulative mass loss was calculated per area of exposed surface (g/m^2). This also allows us to compare these results with the results of the MPs release (g/m^2). For obtaining macro images that characterise the weathering process, the specimens during weathering tests were regularly photographed with an EOS 30D camera (Canon, Japan) equipped with Canon EF-S 17–55 mm lens. The images were taken in a white box under constant artificial lighting with consistent camera settings throughout all tests. Microscopic changes were analysed by optical microscope. Stemi 305 light microscope (Zeiss, Germany) with an integrated camera was used to examine the surface at three fixed locations for six replicates of each sample series. Images were captured at a magnification of $10\times$. Scanning electron microscope (SEM) VEGA TS 5136MN (Tescan, Czech Republic) was used to investigate the degraded surfaces in more detail. The images were obtained at $200\times$, $500\times$, $1000\times$, and $5000\times$ magnification using secondary electron detector, and the accelerating voltage was 15 kV. Before the samples were inserted in the SEM, they were sputter coated with a thin gold layer to prevent charge accumulation on the surface. The apparatus used for gold sputtering was K550X (EMITECH, USA).

Characterisation of the MPs

The collected materials on the sieves were transferred to vials and characterised in bulk to obtain the information about their chemical composition and physical properties. For a comparison, artificial MPs were used. The chemical properties were analysed by ATR-FTIR, and characterisation of microstructure was done by SEM in a similar way as it was explained in the sub-Sect. "2.5". The FTIR spectra were obtained by Nicolet iS50 FTIR Spectrometer (ThermoFisher Scientific, USA)

Fig. 3 Cumulative microplastics (MPs) release from wood plastic composites (WPC1 and WPC2) and recycled polypropylene (rPP) during accelerated weathering (AW)

using attenuated total reflectance (ATR) module with a diamond crystal. For each MPs series, three replicates were used and for each replicate 32 scans were performed in absorbance range $4000\text{ cm}^{-1} - 400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ with a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} . Identical baseline correction was performed on all obtained spectra at the absorption frequencies of 4000 cm^{-1} , 3800 cm^{-1} , 3050 cm^{-1} , 2680 cm^{-1} , 2480 cm^{-1} , 1860 cm^{-1} , and 1500 cm^{-1} . Carbonyl, hydroxyl, and carbon-oxygen (including cellulose) indices were calculated as the ratio of the absorption band area of the corresponding functional group (carbonyl groups ($1650\text{ cm}^{-1} - 1850\text{ cm}^{-1}$), hydroxyl groups ($3100\text{ cm}^{-1} - 3600\text{ cm}^{-1}$), and carbon-oxygen bonds of the polymer including corresponding cellulose peaks of C-O stretching and C-O-C glycosidic linkages of the wood ($900\text{ cm}^{-1} - 1310\text{ cm}^{-1}$) to the absorption band area of the reference band ($1410\text{ cm}^{-1} - 1500\text{ cm}^{-1}$) that corresponds to the vibrations of methylene and methyl groups of the polypropylene backbone [30–33]. This reference band was used also for normalisation of all spectra. A Zeiss Stemi 305 light microscope was used to measure the length and width of the MPs and to calculate the aspect ratio. For the collected MPs, the measurements were taken after the 8th

AW cycle. For each series, at least 150 MPs were measured using Zeiss Labscope software and subsequently used to calculate the aspect ratio.

Statistical analysis

Descriptive statistical analysis was performed to obtain the mean and standard deviation (STDEV) for the data. In all graphical representations, the plotted values correspond to the mean, and the associated error bars represent the STDEV. Statistical significance between sample groups was evaluated using analysis of variance (ANOVA), with a significance threshold of $p < 0.05$.

Results and discussion

Quantification of the eroded particles

The MPs release during weathering (Fig. 3) significantly differed depending on the material and AW cycle. rPP produced a relatively small amount of MPs even during eight AW cycles. Surprisingly, for WPCs a rapid formation of eroded particles started already during the 2nd AW cycle, when the cumulative MPs release exceeded 1 g/m^2 . Further exposure led to a steady increase in particle separation throughout the test, reaching cumulative MPs release of around 4.4 g/m^2 and 9.4 g/m^2 after the 4th and 8th AW cycles, respectively. The results suggest that a higher amount of plastic in a material does not automatically mean that it will release more MPs. A detailed explanation of the reasons for the significantly higher mass of MPs collected for WPCs compared to rPP is discussed in the following sections. The observed cumulative MPs release differed by no more than 7% between WPC1 and WPC2, indicating good reproducibility of the developed process design.

The results concerning the fractional distribution of the collected particles (Fig. 4) show that the released particles are mainly (99%) smaller than $500\text{ }\mu\text{m}$. It agrees with our previous study, where we came to the same

Fig. 4 Size distribution of the collected microplastics at each accelerated weathering (AW) cycle for wood plastic composites (WPC1 and WPC2 (only 4 AW cycles)) and recycled polypropylene (rPP)

conclusion by analysing the degraded surfaces of WPCs made of unmodified and thermally modified pine wood [12]. In a number of environmental studies, it has been reported that MPs found in various matrices are mainly smaller than 1000 μm with the majority around 20–300 μm , however, these studies exclude particles smaller than 20 μm which are difficult to precisely measure [34–36]. The general trend is that a decreasing particle size is associated with an increasing abundance [34].

Initially, the largest amount of eroded particles was collected on the 150 μm and 75 μm sieves for WPCs, but by increasing the number of AW cycles, the share of the particles collected on the 20 μm sieve increased. Such a trend is logical based on the fact that the polymer matrix continues to degrade with increased exposure time, leading to more imminent embrittlement [27]. In addition, the dynamics of MPs formation show that the highest release rate for WPCs is reached during the 3rd AW cycle, after which the amounts gradually decrease. This could be due to the polymer-rich surface that is typical for WPCs if the layer has not been mechanically removed. Degradation of the surface layer initially releases more MPs, but, as this layer erodes exposing the bulk of the WPC, which is the actual WPC composition, a lower and more steady release of MPs occurs.

The visual images of the sieves containing 99% of all eroded particles (Fig. 5) show that there are no indications of wood particle separation. The Py-GC-MS results revealed (Supplementary material S1) that these particles have a very intensive peak corresponding to the polypropylene indicator ion 2,4-Dimethyl-1-heptene (propylene trimer) with the m/z 126 (peak area of 18%–19% from the total peak area), thus confirming that the collected MPs are made of polypropylene. However, the pyrograms (Supplementary material S1) did not show the presence of this indicator ion in the run-off water, which may contain MPs with the size smaller than 20 μm . This was not observed in either the solids of the effluent or the filter paper holding the agglomerates. These results suggest that all eroded MPs were caught on the sieves. Although MPs were not detected in the run-off water,

the photodegradation products characteristic of polypropylene were detected, showing peaks in pyrograms corresponding to ketones, acids, and aldehydes. Researchers have tackled MPs of the size lower than 20 μm in various environments. MPs down to the 1 μm have been studied and quantified for wastewater samples by using stainless steel membranes of 1 μm mesh size [37] and road dust specimens by using a fractionator [38]. Successful methodology has been developed on quantifying also nanoplastics in water samples by Py-GC-MS [39]. Still further advances in this direction are required by validating the existing and development of new methodologies to ensure consistency and reliability of the results [40].

The tests performed in the study are accelerated and simplified by including only UV irradiation and precipitations (water spray), which are considered the most severe stressors. Therefore, such tests cannot be directly compared to weathering in natural conditions as there are also other influencing factors and their combinations such as geographical location, orientation, wind, precipitations, temperature, humidity, air pollution etc. Therefore, further studies are needed that could collect or based on the changes that occur on the surface approximate the formed MPs amount per year during natural weathering. Our previous study has shown that significant surface erosion can already be observed in only a couple of months of outdoor exposure for WPCs without protective additives [12].

Changes in material surface resulting in erosion

Surface images of the weathered samples obtained with optical microscope (Fig. S2-1) and SEM (Fig. 6) clearly show that the first signs of surface erosion with noticeable separation of microparticles can be seen already as early as after the 1st AW cycle for WPCs while only after the 8th AW cycle for rPP. This is in accordance with the results presented in Fig. 3, which show that a detectable amount of MPs was released during the 1st AW cycle for WPCs, while the amount released for rPP remained relatively small even after 8th AW cycles. The optical microscope images (Fig. S2-1) show that erosion

Fig. 5 Microplastics collected on the sieves after the 4th AW cycle for WPCs

Fig. 6 SEM images taken at 200× magnification of wood plastic composite (WPC1) and recycled polypropylene (rPP) surface after accelerated weathering (AW) cycles

Fig. 7 SEM images taken at 1000× and 5000× magnification of the polymer part of the wood plastic composite surface after the (a) 4th and (b) 8th accelerated weathering (AW) cycles

is uniform across the surface, predominantly affecting the plastic phase of the WPC. After the 4th AW cycle, wood particles also separate, as the particles previously present on the surface were no longer there at that point. However, degradation of wood resulting in separation of small wood fibres can potentially occur earlier [41]. SEM images (Fig. 6) reveal intense cracking in the regions where wood particles lie beneath the polymer layer. These regions exhibited more pronounced surface erosion with further exposure. The damage is most likely caused by the swelling and shrinking of the wood particles due to moisture fluctuations, which induce stress on the surrounding polymer matrix. When the stress exceeds the strength of the polymer, microcracks form and facilitate further degradation with eventual MPs separation. Weak adhesion due to chemical incompatibility between the nonpolar polymer and the polar wood particles could explain why MPs erode already at the point of embrittlement for WPCs [42]. For the rPP, only microvoids, appearing as tiny cavities or pores within the material, are discernible after the 1st AW cycle, whereas microcracking occurs during the 2nd AW cycle. The delay is due to smaller internal stresses comparing to WPCs. It has been reported that microcracking begins

with the formation of microvoids, which is followed by cracking [43]. The cracking occurs because of the internal stresses caused by chemocrystallisation resulting from scission reactions that occur during photodegradation. This causes surface embrittlement and is observed also for other semi-crystalline polymers [27, 43]. The microcrack network that forms on the surface consists of wide, deep cracks that create surface segments around 100 µm in size. Within them, a shallower and narrower microcrack network forms, creating surface segments of around 10 µm in size. The latter are clearly observable in images taken at 1000× magnification presented in Fig. 7a. The width of the cracks increases by increasing the exposure time. It has been found that the cracks also become deeper [44].

Further progression of the degradation disrupts the narrow microcrack network, forming an irregular and rough surface made of very small pieces of the remaining plastic matrix with the size of around 1 µm (Fig. 7b). MPs of this size and smaller may be released during weathering. It has been found that at the final stage of degradation of LDPE a considerable amount of highly polar and crystalline nanoplastics are released with the size up to 300 nm [45]. However, in the present study, we did not

detect MPs of the size smaller than 20 μm in the run-off water analysed by Py-GC-MS. Possibly, further fragmentation to MPs of this size may occur at later stages already after these larger pieces of MPs have separated from the material. In the present experiment, the eroded particles were excluded from further weathering. There is a possibility that some of these smaller sized particles were retained on the large MPs due to agglomeration [46]. However, the presence of them could not be clearly identified when analysing the collected MPs with SEM (Sect. “Adsorption and attachment potential”). Adsorption and attachment potential of the colloidal particles to other objects in the system is also possible [45], however not all of them will be adsorbed and some indications of their presence should still be observed in Py-GC-MS.

The mass loss per exposed surface (g/m^2) of all samples is presented in Fig. 8a. The results show that the mass loss significantly increases with an increase in AW cycles reaching the cumulative mass loss of $66.4 \text{ g}/\text{m}^2$ for WPC1 and $36.8 \text{ g}/\text{m}^2$ for rPP. Comparing these results with the MPs release presented in Fig. 8b, a quite significant difference is observed. The difference could be caused by the formation of volatile and water-soluble degradation products as well as leaching of low molecular substances [27, 47, 48]. It has been found that polypropylene during photodegradation releases a considerable amount of volatile compounds such as CO_2 , H_2O , ketones, acids, esters, and aldehydes [47]. In our previous study, where we exposed the same rPP as in this study to UV radiation for 1000 h in a Petri dish, the mass of the evenly distributed powder decreased by 25% just by the formation of volatile degradation products. This corresponded to a mass loss of $45 \text{ g}/\text{m}^2$ of the exposed surface [27]. Total UV irradiation after 8th AW cycles in the present study was 1120 h. The mass loss for the rPP sheet reached $36.8 \text{ g}/\text{m}^2$ of which contribution from the MPs release is only $0.3 \text{ g}/\text{m}^2$. Therefore, the results suggest that the significant mass loss cannot be attributed to the formation of MPs alone as it is not the only factor that can contribute to the mass loss. For this reason, gravimetric analysis by

weighing the exposed samples before and after weathering is not a suitable approach to indirectly quantify the release of MPs during weathering, unlike its application to materials subjected to abrasion.

Characteristics of the collected particles

Chemical composition

A suitable amount of the eroded particles for further analysis were collected only from the WPCs, therefore just these were used for the characterisation of real MPs. The chemical composition of the eroded particles was analysed by ATR-FTIR to understand what material is exactly separating from the surface, how the chemical groups change depending on the weathering cycle, and whether different size particles have different chemical composition. The FTIR spectra of the artificial MPs and the collected particles on the sieves of different mesh sizes after the 4th AW cycle are presented in Fig. 9.

The results clearly show that the absorption bands of the collected particles correspond very well with the main absorption bands of the artificially made rPP powder. These similarities suggest that these particles are mainly made of polypropylene, which is consistent with the Py-GC-MS results, and due to their small size (99% < 500 μm) they are definitely MPs (further referred in the text as the real MPs). However, the real MPs have more variety of functional groups and bonds formed due to the photooxidation of polypropylene through Norrish I and II reactions [49, 50]. The most significant changes occur in the regions of $3100 \text{ cm}^{-1} - 3600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $1650 \text{ cm}^{-1} - 1850 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $1550 \text{ cm}^{-1} - 1650 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, and $900 \text{ cm}^{-1} - 1310 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, which correspond to hydroxyl groups, carbonyl groups, double bonds, and carbon-oxygen bonds, respectively. However, by exposing the artificial MPs to 500 h of UV irradiation it is possible to obtain MPs, which chemically are similar to the real MPs captured on the sieves. The only differences are that the real MPs have more double bonds and slightly different composition and amount of carbonyl groups with higher number of esters. The esters give rise to the shoulders at 1730 cm^{-1}

Fig. 8 Comparison between mass loss of weathered samples (a) and the mass of collected microplastics > 20 μm eroded from these weathered samples (b)

Fig. 9 ATR-FTIR spectra of eroded particles from wood plastic composite (WPC1) collected on the sieves with the mesh size of 20 µm, 75 µm and 150 µm after the 4th AW cycle and artificial MPs

Fig. 10 Carbonyl, hydroxyl and carbon-oxygen (incl. cellulose) indices of real and artificial microplastics (MPs) depending on accelerated weathering (AW) cycle or duration of UV irradiation

– 1735 cm^{-1} and also contribute to the carbon-oxygen bonds region [51]. This may be due to the fact that artificial MPs were exposed to UV radiation under dry conditions, whereas the weathering process also involved water exposure during spray steps, although the samples were never immersed. It has been shown that the medium has significant impact on the photodegradation pathways, where in the air more oxidation reactions occur due to higher oxygen availability comparing to water mediums [52].

The fractions 150 µm and 75 µm of the real MPs are completely identical from the chemical point of view. However, a significant difference is visible in the spectrum for the 20 µm fraction, which have a considerable increase in OH groups (3100 cm^{-1} – 3600 cm^{-1}), double bonds (1550 cm^{-1} – 1650 cm^{-1}) and carbon-oxygen (incl. cellulose) bonds (900 cm^{-1} – 1310 cm^{-1}). These differences indicate that the fraction 20 µm could contain wood fibres, which have eroded from the surface together with the plastic. By analysing the 20 µm sieve fraction with SEM, presence of some fibres was observed

(Fig. S2-2). Considering that the diameter of the pine (*Pinus sylvestris* L.) tracheid is around 25 – 40 µm [53], it is highly probable that these wood fibres are captured on the 20 µm sieve. During UV irradiation, lignin, the polymeric matrix of wood, degrades, releasing the wood fibres [41]. Their presence in the collected and analysed MPs samples can contribute to an increase in absorption in the wavenumber ranges 3100 cm^{-1} – 3600 cm^{-1} and 900 cm^{-1} – 1310 cm^{-1} .

The Fig. 10 shows how the main groups and bonds related to photodegradation change during weathering for the real and the artificial MPs. The results of the fraction 75 µm and 150 µm are combined in a single group (Real MPs 75&150 µm), since the similarity of these fractions was observed for all AW cycles. The spectral absorption of the functional groups associated with the photodegradation process increases with each exposure step for both real and artificial MPs. However, the increase is much more pronounced for the artificial MPs. Interestingly, the carbonyl index for the real MPs does not change much between the AW cycles. It is

around 0.7 after the 1st AW cycle and 0.8 to 1.0 after the 4th and 8th AW cycles. In contrast, the carbonyl index for the artificial MPs increases exponentially with each step reaching 2.7 after 1000 h of UV exposure. For the real MPs, based on the UV exposure alone, AW1, AW2, AW4, and AW8 correspond to 140 h, 280 h, 560 h, and 1120 h of UV irradiation, respectively. The relatively small variation in the carbonyl index of the collected MPs between different AW cycles suggests that MPs detachment from the surface occurs once a critical level of degradation has been reached. This process requires sufficient internal stress (e.g., from dimensional fluctuations of wood particles) and external forces (e.g., from precipitation) acting concurrently. To replicate the real MPs from this perspective, UV irradiation of artificial MPs to equilibrium state of degradation is much too extensive. The optimal exposure time for this specific plastic is 500 h, but it will differ for other types of plastics. The carbonyl index could potentially be used to determine the UV irradiation time required to obtain a chemical composition similar to that of real MPs, as it strongly correlates with the weight-average molar mass that governs the polymer's ductility and microcracking [27, 54]. This approach, however, would require knowledge of the critical carbonyl index at which separation occurs. The significantly larger ($p < 0.05$) hydroxyl and carbon-oxygen bond for the Real MPs 20 μm could be attributed to the presence of wood fibres, which have considerable contribution in both spectral regions especially for the OH groups where much smaller contribution is expected from PP. These results suggest that the MPs released during weathering will be partly oxidised. This is important in toxicological analyses, as pristine and weathered MPs have been shown to differ in concentration, which can influence potential impacts on human health [55]. Therefore, if artificial MPs are prepared and used for further tests, they must be UV irradiated for some time.

Morphological details

The morphological details of MPs, such as their size, shape, and microstructure, can influence their movement and fate throughout the environment, as well as their impact on health when they are ingested or inhaled [56]. Studies have demonstrated that the bioavailability and retention of MPs in living organisms increase as particle size decreases and aspect ratio increases. These characteristics enhance the likelihood of inflammation, oxidative stress, and overall toxicity [57–60]. MPs found in the environment exhibit a wide range of aspect ratios, typically in the range of 1–40, with higher values generally associated with fibrous particles [61]. In contrast, the majority of MP fragments tend to have aspect ratios below four, with the distribution skewed toward lower values, frequently approaching one. Similar finding was reported by Cozzarini et al. having aspect ratio below five for 90% of the collected MPs with the highest frequency between one and two [62]. Since the sources and formation conditions of environmentally collected MPs are often unknown, it remains challenging to identify their origin. To better understand the morphology of MPs released during the weathering of WPCs, the aspect ratio of the collected particles was determined and compared with artificial MPs. The results are presented in Fig. 11.

The results show that most of the MPs are fragments with the aspect ratio between 1.0 and 3.5 with a common tendency that aspect ratio is higher for the 20 μm fraction. These results are consistent with the previously mentioned findings characterising environmental samples. A slight difference was observed between real and artificial MPs, with the aspect ratio of the latter being 3% – 14% higher, depending on the particle fraction. However, this deviation is relatively minor and falls within the range of natural variability observed within a single sample series. As such, it is unlikely to have a significant effect on subsequent impacts. These results suggest that the aspect ratio of artificial and real MPs can be considered comparable.

Fig. 11 Length, width, and aspect ratio of the real microplastics collected during artificial weathering (AW) and the artificial microplastics

Fig. 12 SEM images of microplastics collected on sieves with mesh sizes of **a)** 20 µm and **b)** 150 µm sieves, and **c)** artificial microplastics

In the Fig. 12, SEM images of the real MPs, collected after the 4th AW cycle on the 20 µm and 150 µm mesh size sieves, and artificial MPs after 500 h UV irradiation are presented to demonstrate the microstructure of the two types. A high number of micro-cavities, especially on the faces formed during cracking, marks the surfaces of the real MPs from both sieves. These, most likely, were created due to the water spraying during which certain polymer degradation products were dissolved and washed away leaving voids. The result is a large surface area suggesting a high adsorption capacity, a common characteristic reported for MPs [63]. The surfaces of the artificial MPs, which were not subjected to water, are notably smoother, with only minor protrusions discernible. The observed discrepancies in the surface microstructure of MPs imply the importance of the water factor in mimicking weathering effects on MPs formation.

Conclusions

The study developed a novel method for evaluating MPs formation based on the artificial weathering of materials of interest. This method involves collecting and quantifying MPs by integrating a sieve system and water recirculation into an accelerated weathering device (Q-Lab, USA). The process design enables the determination and comparison of MP release (g/m^2) during weathering of different plastic-based materials. It allows analysis of MPs retained on the sieves ($>20\ \mu\text{m}$) and those present in runoff water ($<20\ \mu\text{m}$). The results showed that the developed process design ensures good repeatability. Significantly higher MPs release was detected for WPC ($9.42\ \text{g}/\text{m}^2$) compared with rPP ($0.32\ \text{g}/\text{m}^2$) when exposed to eight AW cycles, which included a total 1120 h of UV irradiation and 32 h of water spray, demonstrating the high dependence of the released MPs on the type of plastic material. The higher MPs release from WPCs compared to rPP is attributed to the dimensional changes in the wood particles, which induced internal stress. Characterisation of the released MPs from the both materials showed that 99% of the MPs were less than 500 µm in size, with most in the 75–500 µm range.

The share of MPs with the size 20–75 µm increased with exposure time. The collected MPs were partially oxidised with an aspect ratio of 1.0–3.5. These particles had a heterogeneous microstructure differing from MPs produced by cryogenic milling. The collected run-off water did not show any signs of MPs when analysed by Py-GC-MS. The presented process design not only quantifies emitted MPs during weathering from plastic-based products with their specific characteristics, but also collects these MPs, providing an opportunity to investigate their environmental and health impacts in detail. However, further validation with other plastic-based materials should be performed in the future to evaluate the potential and possible limitations in the assessment of MPs emissions by the developed method.

Supplementary Information

The online version contains supplementary material available at <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43591-026-00173-w>.

Supplementary Material 1

Supplementary Material 2

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Author contributions

EK, DC: Conceptualization; EK, DC, IA, GD: Methodology; EK, IA, DC: Writing- Original draft preparation; EK: Visualization; EK, DC, LOV, AV, ES, GD: Investigation; LOV, ES: Data curation; IA, BA: Supervision and resources. All authors reviewed the manuscript.

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Data availability

The datasets used and/or analysed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

Declarations

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

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